

EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION OF POLYIMIDE COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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An experimental investigation was conducted to determine how certain processing parameters affect the thermo-mechanical properties of graphite/polyimide composites. Composite laminates were fabricated from unidirectional prepreg consisting of HTS graphite fibers and PMR-15 polyimide resin. The processing parameters which were investigated were staging or precure, cure pressure, and heating rate. The quality of laminates was judged by photomicrographic examination, measurement of fiber and void content, and mechanical testing. Several different types of mechanical tests were conducted and included tensile, flexural, and short beam shear. Some general conclusions are made regarding the effects of processing parameters on the thermo-mechanical properties of HTS/PMR-15.

Introduction

A large number of advanced fiber composites are currently in use as engineering materials for aerospace and industrial applications. These composites consist of a variety of different fibers and matrix materials. However, the most widely used matrix materials for aerospace applications are epoxy resins. This is true largely because of their high quality and excellent structural performance. In general, the epoxy resins are restricted to applications where the use temperature is below 177°C (350°F). There is a present need for high performance resins which have good mechanical properties at elevated temperatures (up to 315°C (600°F)) and which are relatively easy to process. High performance resins for these applications have been developed and one such type is the polyimides. The technology and data base on these relatively new resin materials is not well established and much development remains to be done in the area of polyimide processing and characterization. This need initiated a recent industry wide assessment of the technology associated with graphite/polyimide (Gr/PI) composite materials by NASA-Langley Research Center (1). This assessment included the current state-of-the-art and the future prospects of these materials, as well as present and future use, availability, processing, manufacturing, and testing of Gr/PI composite materials. The general consensus of this assessment was that the major problems with polyimides are processing difficulties. If these problems can be overcome, polyimides will find more widespread use. The most prominent of these processing problems include: (a) the presence of relatively large voids or porosity, (b) development of cure cycles, and (c) equipment limitations due to higher cure temperatures.

One of the most promising of the polyimide resins in the United States is reported to be PMR-15, which was developed at NASA-Lewis Research Center (2). The term PMR denotes in situ Polymerization of Monomer Reactants and the 15 denotes a formulated molecular weight of 1500. PMR-15 is an addition reaction type of polyimide which emits no volatiles during the final cure cycle and results in a relatively low void content composite. When first introduced, PMR polyimides were considered to be a low flow resin requiring cure pressures in the range of 3450 to 6900 kNm⁻² (500 to 1000 psi) for fabrication of low void composites. Some recent development work has been aimed at improving the processability of PMR-15 so that autoclave cure cycles can be used (3). Only recently, it has been reported that the slower heating rates of from 2.5 to 5°C/min (4.5 to 9°F/min) and relatively low pressures of 345 to 1380 kNm⁻² (50 to 200 psi) which are required for autoclave processing can be applied to PMR polyimide prepreg materials (4). Other recent work conducted on the PMR-15 Gr/PI has been reported in References (5) and (6). These references will not be reviewed in detail in this paper but are given to provide the interested reader with more background information.

The primary objective of the present work was to investigate the effect of several processing variables on the thermo-mechanical properties of PMR-15 polyimide resin reinforced with graphite fibers. This work was experimental in nature and was directed toward the development of a laboratory processing technique which would result in a high quality laminate. The main reason for choosing PMR-15 as the resin system to be studied was because of current NASA interest in PMR-15 as a candidate material system for the U.S. Space Shuttle.

Experimental Procedure

Materials

The polyimide prepreg material used in this investigation was unidirectional HTS/PMR-15 which was supplied by Reliable Manufacturing Company of

Figure 1. Blanket Press for Laminated Panel Processing

Fountain Valley, California. All prepreg material was stored in a plastic bag at -18°C (0°F) until use.

Fabrication

All laminates which were fabricated were either 8 plies or 12 plies in thickness. Two sizes of laminates were made, these being $48.3\text{ cm} \times 30.5\text{ cm}$ and $15.2\text{ cm} \times 15.2\text{ cm}$. Laminate fabrication was accomplished primarily in a blanket or cavity press which is illustrated in Figure 1. A schematic of this apparatus is shown in Figure 2. In principle, this press is very similar to an autoclave and can accommodate a panel up to $76\text{ cm} \times 76\text{ cm}$ ($30\text{ in.} \times 30\text{ in.}$) with pressure to 1035 kNm^{-2} (150 psi) and temperatures up to 315°C (600°F). The press works on the principle that a special rubber "blanket" is placed over the layup, then air pressure is introduced over the blanket to provide a uniform cure pressure over the entire layup surface. The press is much more compact than a autoclave and is an excellent research tool for small panel fabrication. In addition, the use of the blanket press eliminates the necessity of bagging the layup. For polyimide fabrication in an autoclave, conventional bagging materials such as nylon cannot be used at temperatures exceeding 205°C (400°F) except for a short period of time. If an autoclave cure cycle is needed which requires temperatures in excess of 205°C , it is necessary to use a metallic bag of either aluminum or steel for bagging purposes.

The processing parameters which were chosen in this work are shown in

Figure 2. Schematic of Blanket Press

Table 1 and are staging or precure, cure pressure, and heating rate. A basic procedure for staging, cure, and postcure, was developed in this program and is shown in the Appendix. The procedure for laminate layup is illustrated in Figure 3. Observe that a nylon bag is shown, and is used in the vacuum oven for the staging cycle. This bag is removed prior to the cure cycle in the blanket press.

Laminate Testing

Test specimens were cut from the cured laminate panels. Three types of specimens were tested.

- (1) Tensile specimens - Unidirectional specimen of 0 deg. orientation with respect to load were tested under quasi-static load at room temperature to determine stress-strain behavior and ultimate strength. The test specimen and tests were conducted in accordance with ASTM D 3039-74.
- (2) Short beam shear specimens - Unidirectional short beam shear specimens were loaded using a 3-point loading fixture and a span-to-depth ratio of 4.5. The test specimen and tests conformed with

Table I. Processing Matrix

Staging or Precure	Heating Rate °C/Min (°F/Min)	Cure Pressure, kNm ⁻² (psi)	
		345 (50)	690 (100)
2 Hrs @ 205°C (400°F)	22 (40)	X	X
	4.4 (8)	-	X
None	22 (40)	X	X
	4.4 (8)	-	X

Figure 3. Layup For Blanket Press

ASTM D 2344-76 and were conducted at room temperature and 315°C (600°F).

- (3) Flexural Specimens - Unidirectional flexural specimens were tested using 3-point loading and a span-to-depth ratio of either 16 or 20. The test specimen and tests conformed to ASTM D 790-71 and were conducted at room temperature and 315°C (600°F).

Results and Discussion

Processing

The quality of laminates was determined by photomicrographic examination, measurement of void content and fiber volume, and by mechanical testing. The results of the processing matrix are summarized below as Table II where V_f = percent fiber volume and V_v = percent voids. Fiber content was determined by

Table II. Results of Processing Matrix

Staging or Precure	Heating Rate °C/Min (°F/Min)	Cure Pressure, kNm ⁻² (psi)	
		345 (50)	690 (100)
2 Hrs @ 205°C (400°F)	22 (40)	$V_f = 49.69$ $V_v = 9.66$	$V_f = 60.81$ $V_v = 4.15$
	4.4 (8)	-	$V_f = 46.70$ $V_v = 7.49$
None	22 (40)	$V_f = 43.11$ $V_v = 18.24$	$V_f = 46.76$ $V_v = 11.37$
	4.4 (8)	-	$V_f = 55.76$ $V_v = 9.52$

PANEL NO. 4

50X

PANEL NO. 10

50X

Precure	Yes
Cure Pressure, kNm ⁻² (psi)	690 (100)
Fiber Volume, V _f	60.81
Voids, V _v	4.15
Heating Rate, 22°C/min	

No
690 (100)
46.76
11.37

PANEL NO. 11

50X

PANEL NO. 12

50X

Precure	No
Cure Pressure, kNm ⁻² (psi)	345 (50)
Fiber Volume, V _f	43.11
Voids, V _v	18.24
Heating Rate, 22°C/min	

Yes
345 (50)
49.69
9.66

Figure 4(a). Photomicrographs of HTS/PMR-15 Panels No. 4 and 10.
 (b). Photomicrographs of HTS/PMR-15 Panels No. 11 and 12.

Figure 5. % Voids of HTS/PMR-15 Versus Cure Pressure for Heating Rate of 22°C/min and 5°C/min.

digestion in concentrated sulfuric acid and hydrogen peroxide as described in ASTM D 3171-33. Laminate void contents were determined by comparing measured laminate densities to calculated densities based on fiber contents of the laminates. Measured densities were determined by weighing samples in air and de-ionized water as described in ASTM D 792-66. Photomicrographs of several panel cross-sections are shown in Figure 4. The measured void contents and processing parameters are also shown below the figures for reference. The results of Table II are graphically illustrated in Figure 5 for a heating rate of 22°C/min. Also shown are the results of Vanucci (4) for T300/PMR-15 graphite fabric laminates. The results in Reference 4 were obtained from autoclave cured laminates at pressures of 345, 690, and 1380 kNm⁻² (50, 100, and 200 psi), similar staging conditions, and for a heating rate of 5°C/min (9°F/min). As can be seen, the results of the present study and those of Reference 4 are in close agreement for the range of voids and pressures shown for staged prepreg. However, for unstaged prepreg, the present study showed higher voids than for staged prepreg. This was not found to be true in Reference 4 for unstaged material, where a cure cycle with no staging resulted in a lower void content. It appears that the faster heating rate may not allow sufficient time for resin bleedout prior to final cure. Thus, it appears that heating rate is an important consideration for controlling fiber volume. These results also illustrate the importance of staging and pressure on fiber volume and voids and indicate that further study is needed to fully assess the effect of staging on the quality of laminates. Staging is important to the resin flow during final cure and may be a necessary step for obtaining higher fiber volumes. In general, the higher the cure pressure, the lower the voids.

Mechanical Testing

Tensile Tests - The results of the room temperature tests on tensile coupons are given in Table III. The data shown represent the average of four test specimens. These results are in good agreement with the results of Reference 6 where unidirectional tensile strengths ranging from 1170-1380 MNm⁻² (170-200 ksi) were reported for HTS/PMR-15.

Interlaminar Shear Tests - The results of interlaminar shear tests are

Table III. Results of Tensile Tests

Fiber Orientation	Modulus, GNm^{-2} (10^3 ksi)	Strength, MNm^{-2} (ksi)	V_f , %	V_v , %
0 deg.	135.8 (19.9)	1276 (185)	59.22	4.4

shown in Figure 6. Interlaminar shear strength (ISS) is plotted versus cure pressure for staged and unstaged laminates tested at room temperature and 315°C. Each data point represents the average of three tests. As one might expect, the ISS increased with an increase in cure pressure and decreased with increasing temperature. This increase in cure pressure corresponded to a decrease in voids as shown in Table II. It appeared that the ISS was not greatly affected by staging. However, an accurate assessment of the effect of staging on ISS could not be made with the limited amount of test data.

Flexural Tests - The results of flexural tests are shown in Figure 7. Flexural strength is plotted versus cure pressure for staged and unstaged laminates tested at room temperature and 315°C. As was the case for the ISS, the flexural strength increased with an increase in cure pressure and decreased with increasing temperature. For the limited data shown, the percentage increase in ISS and flexural strength for an increase cure pressure was about the same.

Conclusions

1. Of the parameters investigated, cure pressure had the greatest effect on porosity and mechanical properties. An increase in cure pressure decreased the porosity and increased the mechanical properties. Cure pressures of 690 kNm^{-2} (100 psi) or greater are recommended for processing HTS/PMR-15 GR/PI.
2. Heating rate appeared to have an effect on fiber volume, but

Figure 6.

Interlaminar Shear Strength of HTS/PMR-15 Versus Cure Pressure For Heating Rate of 22°C/Min (40°F/Min)

Figure 7.

Flexural Strength of HTS/PMR-15 Versus Cure Pressure for Heating Rate of 22°C/Min (40°F/Min)

did not significantly change the porosity.

3. Staging appeared to have an effect on both fiber volume and porosity. Laminates which were staged prior to cure exhibited a lower porosity than those which were not staged.
4. Further work needs to be conducted on PMR-15 as well as other promising polyimide resins to develop processing techniques which result in high quality laminates.

Acknowledgments

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Appendix Curing Cycles

Staging or Precure Cycle

1. Place layup in cold oven and draw full vacuum (76 cm. Hg). Check for leaks and heat oven to 204°C (400°F).
2. Maintain oven at 204°C for 2 hours under full vacuum.
3. Cool to 65°C (150°F) under vacuum and remove layup from oven.

Cure Cycle

1. Place layup in blanket press and allow part to reach 149°C (300°F) at a specified heat up rate.
2. Slowly apply pressure until 345 kNm⁻² (50 psi) is reached.
3. Raise temperature to 246°C (475°F) and increase pressure to 690 kNm⁻² (100 psi). Hold for 30 minutes.
4. Raise temperature to 260°C (500°F) and hold 30 minutes.
5. Raise temperature to 288°C (550°F) and hold 2 hours.
6. Cool layup to 65°C (150°F) at a specified cool down rate and remove from press.
7. Place layup in oven and heat to 315°C (600°F) and hold for 2 hours.

Postcure Cycle

1. Place layup in oven and postcure for 16 hours at 315°C (600°F).
2. Cool layup to 65°C (150°F) and remove from oven.